

success story

> Pilot 3: Transport Management

Monitoring and forecasting pollution episodes and its impact made by port activity for carbon footprint mitigation

Comparing in-situ main Air Quality Parameters based-forecast and Copernicus Atmosphere Service (CAM5)

Port-city interaction is essential at a regional level in various countries, as ports may represent an **economic boosting** factor considering both traffic of goods and passengers (tourism). However, the **environmental impact** of port activity requires particular attention, especially for big ports nearby cities. **Joint strategies** are necessary in terms of **climate change adaptation and mitigation** among the corresponding port authority, city council and any other regional entity involved in decision-making policies.

Our **pilot 3|Transport Management** partners are developing a web application to support the Balearic Port Authority in their day-to-day environmental monitoring tasks to minimize or reduce their environmental impact by providing insights on the emissions of **main atmospheric** pollutants (NO_2 , SO_2 , O_3 and $\text{PM}_{2.5}$), as well as **optimizing the berthing allocation**. The work has been focussed both on data gathering and processing, AI pollution forecast models building as well as on the UI that supports the decision-making:

- At **data level**, we are now able to *collect and store* in-situ data from various sensors deployed at the BPA and regional level to monitor the main air quality parameters. Based mainly on historical data, we are able to *predict* with *ML techniques* those values for the 24-48 and 72 upcoming hours. The predictions can be then compared with satellite-based predictions from CAM5 (10x10 km) from GEOSS. Also, the use of Sentinel 5P images (5x5km) are being used to have information about NO_2 , SO_2 and O_3 , values in areas with no data from in-situ sensors.
- At **UI level**, we have already deployed an interface where users with different profiles can log in and *visualize EO data* from satellite and in-situ data, including the forecasts. The early (*agile*) development of an UI allows a better interaction with the user in terms of gathering requirements from all different stakeholders.

Useful links:

www.eiffel4climate.eu

<https://www.eiffel4climate.eu/index.php/pilots>

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